

STRAIN VISUALISATION OF COMPOSITE SANDWICH STRUCTURES WITH CORE MATERIALS FOR WIND TURBINE BLADES

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ABSTRACT

Sandwich construction is widely used in wind turbine blades. The core material and the adhesion between the skin and the core can present problems for these structures. The core material can often fail due to shear cracking and delamination after indentation of the skins and/or impact. The aim of this study is to characterize and understand the effect of changing the skin-core configuration on the mechanical response of sandwich structures. Sandwich structures manufactured with Glass-Fibre Reinforced-Polymer (GFRP) skins and PVC core have been tested under static three and four point bend configurations. Four core configurations were tested: (i) Core with a single layer of uniform density, (ii) Core with three uniform density layers, (iii) Graded core with three distinct layers in a high/low/high-density configuration and (iv) Graded core with three distinct layers in a low/high/low-density configuration. The areal densities of these composite sandwich configurations were approximately the same (80 kg/m^3) for all samples, allowing for a direct comparison between the performance of sandwich structures with uniform and graded cores. Results from Digital Image Correlation (DIC) were analyzed to identify the most critical regions in the samples, as well as to understand the effect of changing the core configuration from the strain maps. Results show that the maximum shear strain in the core appears at the layer with the lowest density, which justifies why the samples with graded core sustained lower maximum stresses than the samples with uniform core. Nevertheless, graded-core samples showed a longer plateau at the maximum load and a smoother failure process.

1. INTRODUCTION

Polymeric sandwich composite structures are widely used as lightweight and durable materials for the use in naval, aviation and energy applications [1-4]. Sandwich composite structures used in wind turbine blades and aircraft body components are subjected to considerable damage such as indentation, cracking, delamination and debonding [5-7]. During the operation of a wind turbine, the upper and lower skins of the blades are subjected to cyclic bending induced by wind. Because of bending loads, both skins are generally made of sandwich composites due to their high flexural stiffness to weight

and flexural strength to weight ratios [8]. Sandwich composite structures used in wind turbine blades usually consist of core materials such as polymeric foams and skin materials such as glass-fibre reinforced polymers (GFRP) and carbon-fibre reinforced polymers (CFRP). In the literature, researchers have tried to produce new sandwich composite structures by using various configurations of core and skin materials. There are several studies related with characterization of thermoplastic foam core sandwich structures [9-14].

Steeves et al. [14] investigated the mechanical behaviour of PVC foam core sandwich composites. They performed three point bending (3PB) experiments on a sandwich composite structure made of Divinycell PVC foam and woven glass-epoxy composite prepreg material. The structure was assembled by hand and cured with polyester adhesive at room temperature. They used three different densities of foam, but the foam type was the same. This was to understand the effect of density variation and thickness variation of the sandwich structure on the mechanical properties of the materials, such as compressive and shear strength. They also reported that the most critical failure modes are indentation, core shear cracking and micro-buckling [14].

Battley et al. [11] studied the flexural behaviour of sandwich structures with glass-fibre skins and two different types of PVC foams (Airex R63.80 and Rohacell S51) as core material. Four-point bending (4PB) experiments were performed in accordance with ASTM C393. The test results showed that the mechanical properties of the sandwich materials were indistinguishable before the yield point, and differed only after the onset of damage [11].

Juntikka et al. [12] investigated the behaviour of the materials under compression loading using a 4PB test method with non-crimp glass-fibre skins and two PVC foams with different densities (60 and 100 kg/m³) as core material. The flexural properties of the high-density cored sample were greater than the low-density one, and the deflection of the high-density cored sample was also 2.5 times larger [12].

In the literature, the mechanical behaviour of graded-core sandwich composites (i.e. sandwich structures with varying foam density along the thickness of the core) has not been investigated yet. Furthermore, strain visualisation techniques are rarely used on the investigation of the mechanical response of sandwich composite structures, although they are key to understand the behaviour of the structure and determine which regions are the most problematic. This study aims to investigate the effects of grading the density of the polymeric foam core on the flexural properties of sandwich composites, using strain visualization techniques.

2. MATERIALS AND EXPERIMENTS

The foam used as a sandwich core in this study is AIREX C70, a closed cell, cross-linked PVC [15]. For wind energy applications, this foam is suitable for rotor blades, nacelles, and turbine generator housings. The chosen products are C70.55, C70.75 and C70.90, with properties given in Table 1.

Table 1: Properties of the foam materials used in this study [15].

Foam materials	C70.55	C70.75	C70.90
Density (kg/m ³)	60	80	100
Shear strength (MPa)	0.85	1.2	1.7
Shear modulus (MPa)	22	30	40

Gurit XE603, a +/- 45 biaxial E-glass reinforcement fabric (see Table 2), was used as the reinforcing material for the skins, and a mixture of Prime 20 LV epoxy resin and slow hardener (which is suitable for production of sandwich composite structures) was used as the matrix material. The skins were fabricated using these two materials [16], with three layers of reinforcement in a [0°/90°] / [45°/+45°] / [90°/0°] lay-up. Four types of samples were produced, with the configurations depicted in Table 3.

Table 2: Skin reinforcement description [16].

Manufacturer	Reference	Style	Areal (g/sq.m)	Primary Fibre Type
Gurit	XE603	+/-45 Biaxial Fabric	600	E-glass

Table 3: Configurations of the sandwich composite samples.

Configuration	[80]	[80/80/80]	[60/100/60]	[100/60/100]
Layup	6 layers of glass fibre (in 0/90/-45/+45/90/0 lay-up, total 1800 gsm) with epoxy matrix			
	80g/m ³ foam (15 mm thick)	80g/m ³ foam (5 mm)	60g/m ³ foam (5 mm)	100g/m ³ foam (5 mm)
		80g/m ³ foam (5 mm)	100g/m ³ foam (5 mm)	60g/m ³ foam (5 mm)
		80g/m ³ foam (5 mm)	60g/m ³ foam (5 mm)	100g/m ³ foam (5 mm)
	6 layers of glass fibre (in 0/90/-45/+45/90/0 lay-up, total 1800 gsm) with epoxy matrix			
Average core density (kg/m ³)	80	80	73	87

Resin infusion under flexible tooling (RIFT) was used to manufacture the panels. The panels were cut down to 3PB and 4PB specimens, using a bench saw machine with crosscut saw blade to protect the material from damage during cutting. The nominal dimensions of the samples were 300×75×18 mm. 3PB and 4PB experiments were performed according to ASTM C393 [17] in an Instron testing machine controlled by Bluehill software. The specifications of 3PB and 4PB experiments are given in Table 4.

Table 4: Specifications of 3PB and 4PB experiments.

Span of supporters for both of the rigs	200 mm
Span of the indentors for 4PB rig	100 mm
Diameter of supporters and indentors	12 mm
Velocity of the indentors	6 mm/min

To obtain a better understanding of the response of the sandwich structures, Digital Image Correlation (DIC) was used. This technique tracks a domain of points in an image series captured throughout the test, using the first image of the series as a reference. This allows studying the sample surface deformation and all related strains, as shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1: Schematic illustration of a reference image and deformed image in DIC analysis [18].

A 2D-type analysis was used for the tests, considering displacements in the length-wise and thickness-wise only, hence one of the surfaces of each specimen was speckled with spray paint. Images were acquired every 2 seconds during the test with a GOM Aramis 5M camera, and strain maps were analysed using the Aramis software [19].

Core shear stresses were calculated for each of the samples throughout the test, according to ASTM C393 [17]:

$$\tau_c = \frac{P}{(d+c)b}, \quad (1)$$

where τ_c is the core shear stress, P is the applied load, d is the total sandwich thickness, c is the core thickness, and b is the sandwich width.

The overall specimen deflections were obtained through an optical extensometer tracking the vertical displacement of the indentors and supporting pins. For each specimen, the deflections were shifted by a constant value to ensure a directly proportional relationship with the shear stress within the 300 to 500 kPa range; this was required to discount for the extra compliance provided at the beginning of each test by rubber pads placed between the pins and the surface of the specimen, used to avoid ply damage of the latter.

3. RESULTS

3.1. 3-point bending test

3PB test results of the [80/80/80], [60/100/60] and [100/60/100] configured sandwich composites are given in Figure 2. The graph represents the shear stress in the core (calculated using Equation 1) versus displacement, and the image series indicate the through-the-thickness shear strain (ϵ_{xy}) of the surface during loading.

The overall sequence of events observed in the three configurations tested under 3PB is described below:

1. Initial linear elastic response;
2. Indentation and compressive damage of the foam below the indenter. The load carrying ability is progressively lost, although catastrophic failure does not occur;
3. Shear damage initiation below the indenter;
4. Further indentation and propagation of compressive and shear damage laterally towards the supporters;
5. Load drop due to failure of the top skin for the [80/80/80] and [60/100/60] configured sandwich composites, and shear cracking of the core for the [100/60/100] configured sandwich composite.

The main differences between the results of the different configurations were:

- The location of damage initiation, which occurred at the top layer in the [80/80/80]-configured sandwich composite, and at the weakest layer in both the [60/100/60]- and [100/60/100]-configured sandwich composites;
- The strains were relatively uniform in the [80/80/80]-configured sandwich composites, but localised at the weakest layers in the [60/100/60]- and [100/60/100]- configured sandwich composites;
- The [80/80/80]-configured sandwich composite had the highest shear stress, but the [60/100/60]-configured sandwich composite had the longest plateau.

Figure 2: Comparison of results between all types of core configuration tested under 3PB.

3.2. 4-point bending test

4PB tests were performed with [80], [80/80/80], [60/100/60] and [100/60/100] configured sandwich composites. The strain visualization images and the shear stress versus displacement curves are depicted in Figure 3.

The overall sequence of events observed in the four configurations tested is given below:

1. Initial linear elastic response;
2. Shear damage initiation between the indentors and the supporters;
3. Indentation of the top skin and compressive damage of the core below the indentors;
4. Accumulation of shear damage in the core between the indentors and the supporters, followed by a load drop when a shear crack appeared.

The main differences between the results of the different configurations tested were:

- The maximum shear strain of [60/100/60] and [100/60/100] configured sandwich composites localized at the lowest-density layers. On the contrary, the shear strains were uniformly distributed along the thickness-direction in the [80] and [80/80/80] samples;
- The presence of a weaker layer protected the [60/100/60] and [100/60/100] configured sandwich composites from catastrophic failure, which occurred in the uniform-cored samples;
- A load drop occurred when shear crack appeared in [80]- and [80/80/80]-configured sandwich composites, but not on the graded-core samples.

Figure 3. Comparison of results between all types of core configuration tested under 4PB.

4. CONCLUSIONS

In this study, 3PB and 4PB experiments were conducted on composite sandwich materials with four different core configurations: (i) a single layer of uniform density, represented as [80]; (ii) a uniform core with three uniform-density layers, [80/80/80]; (iii) a graded core with three distinct layers in a low/high/low density configuration, [60/100/60]; and (iv) a graded core with three distinct layers in a high/low/high density configuration, [100/60/100]. The shear strains of the samples were defined using DIC, and the following conclusions can be drawn:

1. 4PB experiments are more representative than 3PB experiments to understand the flexural mechanical properties of sandwich structures. This is because the applied force is shared by two indentors in the former, and therefore indentation is avoided.
2. Digital Image Correlation (DIC) of the samples clearly reveals the shear strain maps during the 3PB and 4PB experiments, which allowed us to understand the effect of the different core configurations on the mechanical properties of sandwich composites, and to determine the weakest region.
3. Regardless of the average density of the core, damage starts and localises at the weakest layer of the core. Consequently, a sandwich structure with uniform core will be stronger than one with graded core with same average density.
4. The maximum specific shear strength of the [60/100/60]-configured sandwich composites is higher than in the [100/60/100]-configured sandwich composites, despite the average density of the [60/100/60] configuration being lower than that of the [100/60/100] configuration. It is concluded that the [60/100/60]-cored sandwich structure is more suitable for wind turbine blades and the aerospace industry, since it is lighter.
5. Considering the 3PB experimental results of the [60/100/60] and [100/60/100] configured sandwich composite structures, changing the configuration of the core does not affect the initiation of shear cracks, but it affects their propagation.
6. From the results of the layered uniform ([80/80/80]) and single-layer uniform ([80]) configurations, the adhesion between the core layers does not fail before the failure of the foam. Thus, layering does not affect the flexural properties of sandwich composite structure, as shown by the identical responses observed in the two cases.
7. In 4PB experiments, the core is less affected by indentation and failure is governed by shearing of the core. In this case, damage will initiate at the weakest layer regardless of its thickness, and therefore the thickness of the weak layers does not affect the flexural strength of graded-core sandwich composite structures.

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